

TABLE I
ANALYSIS 1 & 2 - PATCH VARIABLES

Variable	Description
# Lines Added	Number of lines added
# Lines Deleted	Number of lines deleted
# Lines of Code	Number of lines in the files modified
# Files Impacted	Number of files modified
# Directories Impacted	Number of directories modified
Average Cyclomatic Complexity	Average Cyclomatic Complexity of the files modified
Entropy	Dispersion in lines changed [?]
Is Bug Fixing	Whether or not the patch is for fixing bugs using keyword search (e.g., fix, bug, defect)
Description Length	Number of words in the patch description
# Prior Commits	Number of commits that last touched the lines that are modified in the files modified by the current patch based on the SZZ algorithm [?]
# Prior Commits Bug Fixing	Number of prior commits that are for fixing bugs
Average Prior Commits Age	Average number of days between the prior commits and the current patch
Is Author Core Developer	Whether or not the patch author is a core developer to the project
Is Author Experienced Author	Whether or not the patch author has authored at least 5% of the prior commits
Is Author Experienced Reviewer	Whether or not the patch author has reviewed at least 5% of the prior commits

TABLE II
ANALYSIS 1 - REVIEW DYNAMIC VARIABLES

Variable	Description
# Prior Votes	Number of votes prior to the current review
# Prior Comments	Number of comments prior to the current review
% Prior Votes Positive	Percentage of prior votes that is positive
% Prior Positive Votes From Core Developers	Percentage of prior positive votes that comes from core developers
% Prior Negative Votes From Core Developers	Percentage of prior negative votes that comes from core developers

TABLE III
ANALYSIS 1 - REVIEWER VARIABLES

Variable	Description
Is Reviewer Core Developer	Whether or not the reviewer is a core developer to the project
Is Reviewer Experienced Author	Whether or not the reviewer has authored prior commits in the past
Is Reviewer Experienced Reviewer	Whether or not the reviewer has reviewed prior commits in the past
% Prior Comments By Reviewer	Percentage of prior comments that were made by the reviewer
Reviewer Interaction Frequency w/ Author	Percentage of patches the author has written in the past that were also reviewed by the reviewer

TABLE IV
ANALYSIS 2 - SUMMARY REVIEW VARIABLES

Variable	Description
# Votes	Total number of votes the patch received
# Comments	Total number of comments the patch received
% Positive Votes	Percentage of votes that are positive